

Assessing the impact of demographic dividends on socio-economic growth in our country and the concept of demography

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Annotation: This article is about assessing the impact of demographic dividends on socio-economic growth in our country and the concept of demography, social protection, market economy, demographic processes and their factors, sources of studying demographic processes, activism in democratic change.

Keywords: country, socio-economic, demographic, valuation, dividend, development, innovation.

During the years of independence, taking into account the current real economic and demographic situation, a mechanism of social protection has been created during the gradual transition to a market economy. In the early stages, it was a way to ensure the social protection of the entire population, which in turn allowed to prevent a sharp decline in living standards, to maintain stability in the country. As the reforms deepened, more attention was paid to providing targeted assistance to the population. All types of benefits and assistance began to be provided to families, with the main focus on low-income families, the elderly and children. Differential approaches to different segments of the population are one of the peculiarities of the modern social protection system. The current stage of development of the social protection system in Uzbekistan is based on sustainable economic growth and improvement of the quality of life of the population. The Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, currently approved by the Decree of the President of

the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017. The development of economic activity through the development of its activities serves as a basis for social protection.

Another achievement of the country's social policy is the emergence of a system of social services, the widespread use of modern methods and technologies that allow to provide effective social assistance to citizens in working with the population. Along with the establishment and development of local self-government bodies - the provision of regional social services in the authorities, the training of specialists in the field of social work, social pedagogy and applied psychology, the possibility of providing social services to the population has increased.

In the context of modern Uzbekistan, the system of social services is a system of social and humanitarian activities aimed at the adaptation of individuals, families or groups, social rehabilitation. In the difficult socio-economic conditions of the transition period, Uzbekistan has been able to create a new system of social institutions that will provide the necessary assistance and support to its needy citizens. Care for the elderly, children, and the disabled is provided by the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection, public self-government bodies (neighborhoods), and the Ministry of Internal Affairs. Such institutions include social service centers for various categories of citizens, centers for psychological and pedagogical assistance to the population, social rehabilitation centers for minors, regional centers for social assistance to families, women and children, etc. enters.

Legislation and other normative legal acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan set out the basic principles for the provision of social services to the population. Among them are the following principles: equal access to social services; principles such as the targeting and popularity of social assistance, and social support for the vulnerable. In order to be able to fully cover citizens in need of social assistance at home and to expand the list of services provided to them, self-governing bodies

will be able to provide services at home to single pensioners, the elderly and the disabled. Unemployed citizens are allowed to be temporarily involved in paid public works in order to be employed.

Clearly, it is necessary to organize comprehensive programs to protect and support the population of the country.

The description of the activities of specialists in the field of social work allows us to think about the high demand for them. The country's entry into the market economy itself created a need for social workers. In addition, all social administrations in the country today have specialists without social education. The training of social workers in various other forms of education will help to solve the problem of staffing the state social policy in the country.

In any case, the definition reflects the orientation of values, the positions of the social worker, theories of the nature of social work, for example, sociological theories about the role of the profession in society or its relationship to other disciplines. . Here is one definition: social work is the process of professionally assisting an individual, group, or community to strengthen or restore their ability to express themselves in social life, and to create the most favorable social conditions for them. is an activity that consists of. Special theories of social work seek to describe, explain, and evaluate the work done by social workers. The foundations of social work theory are often expressed in sequence and coherence, as in the social sciences.

Like the medical profession, there are general principles and principles, but special skills and knowledge are required for a social worker specializing in this or that field. Social work is a multidisciplinary profession. This means that in order to help the client, the social worker forms a system of interaction with representatives of other specialties - doctor, educator, psychologist, police officer.

The main unit of observation in demography is the human being. During a person's life, his physiological and psychological characteristics, education, level,

marital status, occupation, qualifications, social group, place of residence, and language skills change. It is this combination of changes in individual life that leads to socio-economic and demographic changes in the lives of the population as a whole. As a result of marriage, the number of families will increase, and the number of singles and single people will decrease. The annulment of marriage, that is, the process of divorce, leads to an increase in the proportion of infertile families and widows in the population. There are times when a person is born. It is during this period that he grows up. Passes from infancy to childhood, adolescence, youth to middle age, adulthood. With the end of each school year, the number of educated people in the population increases. In this way, changes in a person's life lead to changes in the population. Migration is the movement of people from one area to another, which affects the population and composition of these areas.

The population is constantly changing due to births and deaths. Birth rates throughout the world have dropped dramatically already, as has the death toll. Births and deaths are the result of natural population growth. If the number of births is higher than the number of deaths, the population will increase, and vice versa, if the number of deaths exceeds the number of births, the population will decrease.

It is known that in society, for some reason, a part of the population dies. Another part of the population is born. The place of the dead in society is filled at the expense of the newborn, and generations pass. This process is the basis for population regeneration.

In a given region, the composition of the population in a given period is the result of the regeneration of the population in the previous period, and the ground for the regeneration of the population in the next period. This means that population regeneration is a continuous, complex process of social development.

As a result of population regeneration, the population and its age and sex composition are constantly changing. The sex of newborns leads to certain changes in the sex composition of the population. The death toll affects the age structure of the population. Changes in the age and gender composition of the population lead to certain social problems in society. The process of population regeneration, in turn, is influenced by a number of socio-economic factors. Therefore, the process of population regeneration has its own characteristics and laws at each stage of development of society. The main subject of demography is the analysis of the laws of population reproduction.

In studying the population, demography as a separate science provides an excellent analysis of its quantitative and qualitative characteristics.

Quantitative characteristics of the population are expressed in the change (increase or decrease) of the population of a particular nation, region. Qualitative characteristics of the population are mainly expressed in terms of health and education of the population of a particular nation or region, in order to live an average life.

Both processes, quantitative and qualitative development of the population, are closely interrelated. For example, higher levels of public health lead to lower mortality and longer life expectancy. As a result, the population will grow. Also, very high birth rates often lead to a weakening of the mother's and baby's body and an increase in deaths.

From the earliest stages of society's development to the present day, the population of each region has changed steadily, both quantitatively and qualitatively. Demography studies quantitative and qualitative changes in the population as key factors in population regeneration.

Population regeneration, in the broadest sense, natural increase, death, migration, movement of the population across regions, the transition from one social group to

another, access to information, the beginning of labor, and so on. as a result, the composition of the population will be updated.

Demography focuses on the process of natural generational change — the rebirth of a population based on birth and death. This process studies the laws of society at different stages of development, the characteristics and factors of different nations, regions and states, identifies problems and determines the future. In order to fulfill these tasks, demography must study in detail the stages of development of society, the historical conditions. Birth is of particular importance in the structure of demographic processes. This is because the existing population under study was born primarily as a result of birth. Demography studies eclipse as a separate, demographic ground for population regeneration, analyzing all the socio-economic and natural factors that affect it. Demography also focuses on demography as a key element in population regeneration. In the regeneration of the population, first of all, the formation of the family is important. Because most people born in the world are born in a family, in a family environment, they are formed as individuals and start their demographic activities (marriage, having children).

The formation of a family, in turn, is closely linked to the process of marriage and divorce. Demography examines the evolution of marriage and the role of 4 in population regeneration.

Divorce is also a demographic process that affects the reproduction of the population. As demography studies this process, it analyzes in detail a number of causes and effects that affect its level of existence.

Demography also studies the movement of people from one place to another. However, in studying this process, in contrast to the geography of the population, the main focus is not on the regional characteristics of the migration process, but on the changes in the demographic situation of the region that occur as a result of this process.

In demography, the family is studied as a major socio-demographic group. The role of the family in the development of society, its evolution, the main activities of the population in the reconstruction and its factors of change, its consequences are studied, and the main directions of future development are identified.

It is well known that population is the sum of the generations that exist as a result of birth and death. All the demographic processes that make up a person's existence — eclipse, death, marriage, and divorce — occur at a certain point in his or her life, that is, at a certain age.

Therefore, age is a key criterion in the study of demographic processes. In a person's demographic and social status, age and gender are key indicators throughout their lives. The gender composition of the population is also one of the main criteria influencing the demographic situation, which requires demographic analysis.

In the development of demographic forecasts, the science of demography first analyzes in detail the demographic tendencies (attitudes towards demographic processes) of the population of the studied region or social group, and on this basis shows the expected changes in demographic processes.

Developing the content and measures of demographic policy is a very responsible and complex process. In carrying out this work, demography must thoroughly study the level of socio-economic development, ethnic characteristics, customs and values, demographic situation of the state or individual region under study.

Demography, as an independent science, has its own methods of development. These include historical comparison, statistics, mathematics, cartography, logical thinking, and sociological methods. The analysis method of demography is different from statistics. It also examines future quantitative and qualitative changes in the population based on the widespread use of abstract thinking. Because the population is subject to certain social lifestyles, demographic processes also depend on certain production patterns and attitudes. The population

is a product of complex social and natural development, so the population increases due to various factors. In this respect, the subject of demographic analysis is close to the subject of political economy, sociology, psychology, mathematics, statistics, social hygiene, geography, medicine, history, ethnography and other disciplines, and uses the achievements of these disciplines. At the same time, it provides them with valuable information.

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